

Correlational Research of Mothers' Knowledge and Behaviour on The Incidence of Acute Respiratory Infections in Toddlers at The Abepura Community Health Center, Papua

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ABSTRACT

Several middle- to low-income countries experience deaths from acute respiratory infections (ARI) at a very high rate, reaching 4 million people per year. In Indonesia, acute respiratory infections (ARI) remain a serious health problem, with Papua recording the highest prevalence (8.5% in 2023), far above the national average (5.1%). Several factors that influence the incidence of ARI include awareness of the disease and proper treatment. When ARI occurs in toddlers, the most important parties are their parents, especially the mother, as the child's primary caregiver. This study aimed to investigate the influence of mothers' knowledge and behaviour regarding ARI on the incidence of ARI in toddlers in the working area of the Abepura Community Health Center, Papua. This research was conducted using a questionnaire instrument consisting of an informed consent section, respondent personal data, knowledge of ARI and attitudes towards ARI. The result showed demographic data of respondents and the incidence of ARI had no relation with mothers' knowledge and behaviour about ARI and the treatment (indicated by the significance value > 0.05). The absence of this relationship may be influenced by the heterogeneous number of samples per category, and the perceptions and respondents' personal conditions.

KEYWORDS: Acute Respiratory Infection; Behaviour; Knowledge; Papua

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INTRODUCTION

Rapid urbanization in various regions, including Papua, increases the risk of exposure to air pollution and population density, which can accelerate the spread of ARI [1].

Several middle- to low-income countries experience deaths from acute respiratory infections (ARI) at a very high rate, reaching 4 million people per year. This includes Central American countries, where it is estimated that 11-22% of deaths are in infants and 3% in adults aged 14-49 years, contributing significantly to global mortality [2]. In Indonesia, acute respiratory infections (ARI) remain a serious health problem, with Papua recording the highest prevalence (8.5% in 2023), far above the national average (5.1%) [3].

According to Agus's study (2023), the Abepura market area has developed into a densely populated settlement with kiosks, shophouses, and rental houses crowded together. This density triggers air pollutant concentrations (PM 2.5

reaching $38 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), which is far from the WHO safe threshold ($10 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and the Indonesian national standard ($35 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) [4]. The main sources of this pollution include motor vehicle emissions and the burning of household waste. It is reported that 54.5% of households still dispose of waste carelessly. This impacts exposure to ARI pathogens, which increases 2-3 times in toddlers in dense settlements. Unorganized waste disposal and stagnant water become sources of secondary diseases [5].

Based on the results of a survey in the Abepura Community Health Center work area, it was found that 75.1% of households in RW 01, Abepantai sub-district, had inadequate home ventilation [6]. This condition causes poor air circulation and the accumulation of indoor pollutants, including PM 2.5 particles and pathogenic microorganisms [7]. According to [8], houses with inadequate ventilation have a 1.5 times higher risk of ARI in toddlers compared to houses with good ventilation. Houses with dirt floors

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(27.8%) and dirty environments (63%) increase the risk of droplet transmission by up to 1.7 times due to the accumulation of dust as a medium for carrying infected particles [6].

Preliminary research stated that the incidence of ARI in toddlers in an area is significantly influenced by parental knowledge and attitudes regarding ARI and its treatment. Research by [9] in Lewoleba, East Nusa Tenggara, Indonesia, found that mothers with high knowledge had a 2.31 prevalence ratio (PR) for good ARI-related behaviors compared to those with low knowledge. In contrast, those with positive attitudes had a 1.52 PR for such behaviors. Research in the Tangerang region by [10] reveals that 94 respondents (52.2%) had a high level of knowledge, and 131 respondents (72.8%) had good behaviors about ARI and ARI's treatment. This research also showed significant association between parents' knowledge and behaviors against ARI incidence ($p=0.007$) and ($p=0.038$), respectively.

Based on the existing conditions and preliminary research, there is a research gap: no research has examined the relationship between maternal knowledge and attitudes and the incidence of ARI among toddlers in the Abepura Community Health Center's work area. Therefore, the current study aimed to determine whether maternal knowledge and attitudes about ARI influence the incidence of ARI in toddlers in the Abepura Community Health Center's work area.

METHOD

Study Design and Sample

The research design was quantitative analytical research with cross-sectional approach. Cross-sectional research is a type of research that emphasizes the measurement of survey data for independent and dependent variables only once at a time. The population in this study was all mothers bringing toddlers (1-5 years old) who visited and received treatment at the Abepura Community Health Center. Data from the Abepura Community Health Center was collected for the last three months (October-December 2025).

The sampling method used in this study was accidental sampling, namely selecting respondents who are willing and meet the inclusion criteria during the research. Based on the calculations carried out using the Slovin formula, the required sample size was 316, out of a total population of 1511. The inclusion criteria set for respondents were mothers who had toddlers aged 1-5 years who came for treatment and who visited the Abepura Community Health Center, and who were willing to be respondents as stated in the informed consent form.

Instruments

The instrument used to achieve the objectives of this study was a questionnaire consisting of four sections. The first

section was an informed consent form to ensure the community's willingness to participate. The second section was a form to identify respondents' demographic data. The third section was a form to assess mothers' knowledge about ARI and its treatment. The fourth section was a form to assess mothers' attitudes toward ARI and its treatment. This questionnaire was tested for reliability and validity to ensure the instrument actually measured what it was supposed to measure (valid) and provided consistent results over time (reliable) [11].

To quantify the knowledge questionnaire, the Guttman scale was used, namely, the respondent's answers are limited to "Correct" or "Wrong". The answer "Correct" is given a "1" and the answer "Wrong" is given a score of 0 on favourable questions (questions number 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 9, 11, 12, 13, 14, and 15). For unfavourable questions (question numbers 5, 8, and 10), the answer "Wrong" is given a score of 1, and the answer "Correct" is given a score of 0. Patients are said to have good knowledge if they get a score of 76-100%; sufficient knowledge if they get a score of 60-75%; and poor knowledge if they get a score of less than 60% [12]. The behavior questionnaire used a Likert Scale, namely strongly agree, agree, disagree, and disagree. Patients are said to have good behavior if they get a score of 76-100%; sufficient behavior if they get a score of 60-75%; and poor behavior if they get a score of less than 59% [13].

Study Ethical Approval

This study involves human participants. The study was designed in conformance with the ethical principles in the Declaration of Helsinki; ICH guidelines for Good Clinical Practice; ISO 14155:2011; and all applicable local regulations. The study protocol and informed consent documents were reviewed and approved by Research Ethics Committee of Muhammadiyah University of Banjarmasin with certificate number 511/UMB/KE/VIII/2025. This approval is required to ensure that the entire research series and instruments are appropriate and do not harm any party, especially the research subjects [14].

Statistical Analysis

The results were presented in percentages (%), and the average (mean), along with the standard deviation (SD), was provided. The statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software version 22. Bivariate analysis was conducted using the Pearson Chi-Square test to identify significant relationships between demographic and independent variables (knowledge and behavior), against the dependent variable (incidence of ARI in toddler). Pearson Chi-square and p-values were used to determine the strength and significance of these relationships [12].

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RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A total of 324 respondents participated in this study. The demographic data of the study respondents can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Demographic Data of Respondents

Relational analysis results of knowledge and behaviour levels and respondents' age were shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Relational Analysis of Knowledge and Behaviour Levels and Respondents' Age

Levels of Knowledge and Behaviour	Age					Sig. Value
	20-24	25-29	30-34	35-40	>40	
Good Knowledge (n=265)	43	64	78	40	40	0.666
Sufficient Knowledge (n=59)	9	13	18	13	6	
Poor Knowledge (n=0)	0	0	0	0	0	
Positive Behaviour (n=x)	27	45	53	25	24	0.772
Negative Behaviour (n=x)	25	32	43	28	22	

The data in Table 1 showed that there is no relationship between knowledge and attitudes regarding ARI and the age of respondents, because there is no clear pattern in terms of the level of knowledge, attitudes of respondents and age of respondents. A 20-year-old mother is considered to have reached sufficient emotional and physical maturity [10] explain that as age increases, responsiveness and thought patterns develop, resulting in enhanced knowledge. The older a person gets, the wiser they become, the more information they encounter, and the more they experience, thus increasing their knowledge.

Relational analysis results of knowledge and behaviour levels and respondents' education were shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Relational Analysis of Knowledge and Behaviour Levels and Respondents' Education

Levels of Knowledge and Behaviour	Education				Sig. Value
	a	b	c	d	
Good Knowledge (n=265)	19	18	143	85	0.636
Sufficient Knowledge (n=59)	7	4	32	16	
Poor Knowledge (n=0)	0	0	0	0	
Positive Behaviour (n=x)	15	14	91	54	0.742
Negative Behaviour (n=x)	11	8	84	47	

Description:

- a: Elementary School
- b: Junior High School
- c: Senior High School
- d: Higher Education

The data in Table 2 showed no relationship between knowledge and attitudes regarding ARI and respondents' education level. This lack of correlation is due to the heterogeneity of data in each category.

A mother's educational status, theoretically, significantly influences her knowledge and attitudes, as formal education provides access to and the ability to understand important health information. Mothers with high school and college educations tend to have better knowledge of nutrition and child health, making them better able to implement parenting patterns that support growth and prevent disease.

Relational analysis results of knowledge and behaviour levels and respondents' occupation were shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Relational Analysis of Knowledge and Behaviour Levels and Respondents' Occupation

Levels of Knowledge and Behaviour	Occupation					Sig. Value
	a	b	c	d	e	
Good Knowledge (n=265)	179	45	23	4	14	0.890
Sufficient Knowledge (n=59)	41	9	6	0	3	
Poor Knowledge (n=0)	0	0	0	0	0	
Positive Behaviour (n=x)	116	29	15	4	10	0.440
Negative Behaviour (n=x)	104	25	14	0	7	

Description:

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- a: Housewife
- b: Civil Servant
- c: Self-Employed
- d: Healthcare Professional
- e: Enterpriser

The data in **Table 3** showed no relationship between knowledge and attitudes regarding ARI and the respondents' employment level. The presence of housewives who spend more time at home allows for optimal supervision of toddlers, thus playing a crucial role in preventing Acute Respiratory Tract Infections. Research by [15] showed that housewives are more active in preventing ARI than working mothers, although working mothers with family support can still carry out their caregiving role well. Factors influencing this role include time available for childcare, family support, knowledge about ARI, and the ability to manage parenting patterns and a healthy home environment. Direct maternal involvement has a positive impact on toddler health through breastfeeding, immunization, maintaining cleanliness, and avoiding exposure to harmful smoke

Relational analysis results of knowledge and behaviour levels and incidence of ARI were shown in **Table 4**.

Table 4. Relational Analysis of Knowledge and Behaviour Levels and incidence of ARI

Levels of Knowledge and Behaviour	Incidence of ARI		Sig. Value
	With ARI	Without ARI	
Good Knowledge (n=265)	101	164	0.544
Sufficient Knowledge (n=59)	24	34	
Poor Knowledge (n=0)	0	0	
Positive Behaviour (n=x)	69	105	0.761
Negative Behaviour (n=x)	57	93	

The data in **Table 4** showed no relationship between knowledge and attitudes regarding ARI and incidence of ARI in toddlers. ARI is common in toddlers because their immature immune systems make them susceptible to infection. Other contributing factors include environmental and behavioral factors, such as exposure to cigarette smoke, poor home ventilation, poor nutritional status, poor environmental hygiene, and lack of complete immunizations. These factors interact to increase the risk of ARI. ARI control requires improved nutrition, complete

immunizations, and reduced exposure to environmental risks [15], [16]

Furthermore, maternal knowledge, particularly regarding ARI prevention, nutritional fulfillment, and access to health services, significantly impacts the incidence of ARI in children. [17] emphasized that high morbidity and mortality are not solely due to a mother's low level of education, but also to practical ignorance in providing nutritious food and delays in taking children to health facilities. In other words, adequate knowledge about ARI prevention (e.g., handwashing, mask use, and early symptom recognition) can reduce the risk of complications, even in mothers with limited educational backgrounds.

Not only knowledge, but also a mother's attitude is a determining factor in preventing and treating ARI in children. While knowledge provides a foundation for understanding risks and solutions, attitude reflects a readiness to act based on that knowledge, such as diligently implementing health protocols or responding quickly to take a child to a medical facility when symptoms appear [18].

ARI in toddlers can be prevented and managed in several ways, including maintaining a clean home environment and ensuring air circulation through windows, doors, and ventilation. Poor ventilation leads to the accumulation of moisture, dust, and kitchen smoke, which can compromise a toddler's immune system [19]. High levels of outdoor air pollution also trigger respiratory tract irritation [20]. Furthermore, the presence of cigarette smoke in the home is a dominant risk factor, triggering irritation and significantly increasing the incidence of ARI in toddlers [21].

Preventive measures and management of ARI in toddlers include maintaining regular hygiene. Regularly cleaning the house and regularly washing children's toys effectively break the chain of germs [22]. Promote handwashing. Consistent handwashing with soap is a key WHO recommendation, scientifically proven to reduce respiratory infections [23]. Provide complete immunizations. Immunization has been scientifically proven to build the immune system in toddlers, significantly lowering the risk of ARI [24], [25]. Current immunizations for ARI include the influenza vaccine, PCV (Pneumococcal Conjugate Vaccine), Hib (Haemophilus influenzae type b), and DPT (Diphtheria, Tetanus, and Pertussis) vaccine.

Maintain hydration at home. When a child starts to get sick, providing sufficient fluids (water, soup broth, oral rehydration salts) is the most important non-pharmacological (drug-free) intervention from IDAI to thin phlegm, reduce fever, and prevent hospitalization [26].

The role of the family in managing ARI in children is crucial. This role can be implemented through early detection of ARI. The majority of mothers (>95%) already recognize the basic symptoms of ARI (cough, runny nose, fever), which is crucial for early detection (Saldi et al.,

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2024). Time & family support. Housewives have more flexible time to supervise their children, while working mothers can still optimally prevent ARI if they have adequate family support [27], [28]. Responsively take toddlers immediately to the community health center. This can increase the success of therapy [29]. However, stigma, fear of transmission, and misconceptions often cause mothers to delay seeking treatment, which actually worsens the toddler's condition [30], [31]. Avoiding misconceptions about treatment. There are still approximately 19.1% misunderstandings regarding transmission, as well as a widespread misconception among the public that antibiotics are mandatory for all respiratory infections due to a lack of equitable education [32], [33]. Therefore, comprehensive education regarding ARI is still needed by local health workers to create communal knowledge about ARI

CONCLUSIONS

Respondent characteristics and the incidence of ARI in toddlers in the Abepura Community Health Center work area were not related to the level of knowledge and attitudes of respondents regarding ARI and its treatment. The absence of this relationship may be influenced by the different number of samples per category, and influenced by the perceptions and personal conditions of the respondents.

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